

Assessment of Job Satisfaction and Work Performance among Librarians in Academic Libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract:- This research work was carried out to assess the level of Job satisfaction and work performance among academic librarians in Kebbi State tertiary institutions. The work was sponsored by Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) under Institutional Based Research (IBR) component of the programme. The general objective of the study is to find out the level of job satisfaction and work performance among academic librarians in Kebbi state tertiary institutions. Five research questions guided the study. The study was restricted to Librarians and Senior Library Officers in seven (7) tertiary institutions in Kebbi state. The instrument used for data collection was a structured Questionnaire titled Job Satisfaction and Work Performance among Librarians Questionnaire (JSWPLQ). Related literatures were reviewed for the purpose of this study. The questionnaire was administered to the targeted population with the help of 8 trained research assistance. Responses to the items in the questionnaire were analyzed using frequency counts and mean with a mean score of 2.50 as the benchmark. Any mean score from 2.50 and above indicates that the respondents agreed on that item and any mean score below 2.50 indicates disagreement. The results from the findings showed that there is commendable level of job satisfaction among the librarians; the librarians do not resort to lateness to work, abandoning duty when they are not satisfied with their job, friendly subordinates and positive working environment are some of the factors responsible for job satisfaction. Lack of opportunities for socialization and promotion is some of the problems associated with job satisfaction, and annual leave, medical coverage, friendly and competent subordinates are some of the strategies for encouraging and enhancing job satisfaction. It is recommended that the librarians in these academic libraries should be encouraged through sponsorship to attend workshops, conferences and seminars as these will enable them acquire more knowledge and competence. The researchers further recommended that annual leave and medical coverage should be made a regular benefit for the librarians; it was also recommended that the need for recruitment of more qualified Librarians to strike a balance of Librarians/User ratio to make the Library services more effective.

Keywords:- Satisfaction, Performance, Librarians, Senior Library Officers, Academic Library, Job Description Index (JDI).

I. INTRODUCTION

Education and library are the two faces of same coin. One cannot exist without other. Hence, an academic library is an integral part of any institution of formal education. Academic library can be defined as “a library which associated or attached with any educational institution to support its educational programmes”. Academic libraries can also refer to all the libraries that exist in institutions of higher learning ranging from universities, polytechnics, colleges of Education, and any other form of tertiary institution. Their major aim is to provide the curricular educational needs of the students and the entire academic community, example, supporting the teaching staff in the up – to – date materials required for their teaching jobs. Since the Nigerian independence in 1960, the academic libraries have not been accorded the position they deserve, owing partly to the disruption of political leadership, poor economic situation, and nonchalant attitude of the parent institutions. Moreover, the librarians who have managed the libraries have not been so concerned about how their libraries should look like in terms of architectural designs and resources improvement [1]. According to him, the site of a library should permit sufficient space for ornamental trees, a good drainage system, elaborate parking lot, toilets, and lots more. In the context of this study, it is important to consider the welfare/ happiness of the librarians while planning, for the academic library environment putting into account, the furnishing of their offices, good toilets and so on.

One of the biggest factors that are affecting the environment of academic libraries today is the inability of the government to contract the establishment of library architecture/buildings to the professionals (Librarians) hence “out of annoyance, the librarians usually abandon such contractors and never bothered about what is happening. Since the librarians are not mentioned in the statutes in the establishment of libraries, they do not form part of the decision making body in the ministry of education. They usually feel disillusioned to contribute to the design of the library buildings even when they have ideas on better things to do [1].

The primary objective of an academic library is to offer those who may be said to constitute its primary clientele (the faculty, students and academic staff of the institution), the academic and research services in support of the programs of the university of which it is part [2]. The objectives of academic libraries as outlined by [3] are as follows:

- To supply books, periodicals and other materials needed by students and staff in all the subjects of study which the institution offers to the required levels. This sets the framework within which the academic rather than a public library has to justify its presence and be related to students needs and be related to research in the courses which the institution offers.
- To provide support for the teaching and research of the members of the staff in the same subject, with regards to facilities available in other libraries. It is proper that staff should have support for work and research in subjects taught in the institution. With the tremendous developments taking place in a new scheme and methods, it is vital that academics should see research work as always relevant and beneficial to the local and international needs.
- To provide for a wide range of background reading of books and periodicals both in subjects close to those of the curriculum and in more general cultural fields. Each librarian will assess needs variously here. The library should provide materials to support the various programs offered by the institution.
- To help students to become familiar with the library stock. The ability of many students to use the academic library in an adequate and efficient way should be the concern of many academic libraries.
- To help with the day – to – day needs of the users by supplying them with ready reference information and special materials about the locality where the institution is located.
- To act as a link with world of books and library outside its own institution being ready to draw up the special resources of many other institutions and to make its own contribution to the various co – operative schemes.
- To provide guides, lists of additions, current awareness services, reading lists and other publications, and to hold displays and exhibitions of library materials inside and outside the library in order to reinforce the teaching of staff and illustrate the libraries resources.

The following are the major functions of academic libraries:

- Conservation of knowledge and ideas: Every academic library is supposed to conserve knowledge and ideas by acquisition of materials written by different authors throughout the world. These materials could be books, journals, and non book materials which have relevant information to satisfy the information needs of the students and the entire academic community. It is when the librarians are not satisfied that most of them will start exhibiting the I don't care attitude which affects most importantly the shelf reading.
- To fulfill both the needs of the instructional program of the parent institution and the research needs of the students, faculty staff members and people outside the academic community through the collection and acquisition of knowledge in all formats.
- To organize knowledge for easy storage and retrieval – the technical process which include ordering, receiving, accessioning, cataloguing, classification and preparing materials have always been the primary services performed by academic libraries. Though patrons are not aware of

these essential services hence it is referred to as “behind the scene services [2]

- Making resources available to users and preserving knowledge for posterity. In supporting the instructional and research needs of their students and faculties, the academic libraries provide maximum access to collections.
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- Publication: an academic library is expected to publish occasionally, some important works done by their staff or even those outside. In addition, academic library staff can give technical assistance to academic staff outside the libraries who might want to publish bibliographies, indexes and abstracts and does not know how to do it.

Academic librarians are the people or persons in charge of the academic library, library workers trained in the field of library science or librarianship with at least first degree, they are the people to whom the collection, preservation, use and transmission of information and knowledge are entrusted, [4]. Apart from the above note, academic librarians are faced with other duties like, ensuring the development of a balance collection, oversees services to the library clientele, administers staff, prepares library budget, plans new library building or maintenance of an old one., prepares annual report, co-ordinates library development programs. The librarians after carrying out the above functions ought to be motivated. To achieve maximum input to the library services.

- suggested the following motivational points:
- Good remuneration
- Physical conditions (improved environment)
- Hours of service (by the library system)
- Hours of work (by individual staff)
- Leaves of absence (vacation and sick leave)
- Promotion and tenure
- Retirement benefits
- Dismissal of unworthy/ incompetent staff.

From the fore going, it is obvious that if the librarians are not motivated appropriately, they would not be satisfied with their jobs and the consequences could result to not coming to work early, irregular shelf reading, I don't care attitudes by the academic librarians and more. These would not be felt by the students alone but also by the lecturers and the entire academic community because the library is the brain of every institution and the librarians are the driving forces.

The exploration of job satisfaction has received much consideration from both employers and researchers alike. Derived from the field of psychology, it is thought that the ability to establish achievement of basic aspects of life will also extend to other aspects of a person's life [5]. Interest in job satisfaction and research related to it has been heavily investigated in hopes of finding means to increase achievement and productivity in the workplace. Job satisfaction is defined as a positive emotional response toward various facets of one's job or experiences with the job [6]. Most often associated with motivation and life

satisfaction, understanding the level of job satisfaction in students can be beneficial in exploring academic performance. A recent study suggested that students who worked and felt satisfied with their job had better academic achievement [4].

Job performance can lead to job satisfaction. Job performance on the other hand, is a factor of other variables such as technology, ability, supervision and motivation. Job Description Index (JDI) isolated five factors that influenced job satisfaction. Smith observes that job satisfaction must be considered as a feeling, which has arisen in the worker as a response to the total job situation. It is equally true that job satisfaction is influenced by opportunities open to the worker. An employee who has limited alternative job opportunities are bound to rationalize on this and derive satisfaction from what he has available. Another employee who has opportunities is bound to complain and constantly think of his opportunity cost and this affects his total job satisfaction. The usefulness of the JDI is that the scale used has proven discriminate and convergent validity. These five factors were:

A. *Work on the Present Job*

It is believed that one of the major factors that influence job satisfaction is work on the present job. The JDI attempts to find out if the job is fascinating, routine, satisfying, boring, pleasant, tiresome, challenging or frustrating. Whether an employee works hard or not, derives satisfaction from the job or not, is influenced by the way he perceives the work [7].

B. *Present Pay*

According to Herzberg, money is a dissatisfier despite the fact that people have a sentimental attachment to it. As pointed out, money can be seen as a symbol of achievement, success, status, prestige or power, above all there are some people who have to work in order to maintain a large family or to meet their physiological needs. Possession of a large amount of money gives one a feeling that one has control over one's environment. The JDI scale tries to find out from an employee if the pay is adequate, or less than he deserves.

C. *Opportunity for Promotion*

An average employee looks forward to the day when he will earn a promotion. Promotion is a reward for past performances, an encouragement to nudge him to continue to excel. It is a vote of confidence and a blessing. Promotion is a motivator of behaviour. An employee who is denied promotion for a long time gets frustrated. The way an employee perceives his opportunity for promotion influences his job satisfaction. Thus the JDI solicits information from the employee on such issues as whether there is opportunity for promotion, a dead end job, unfair promotion policy, promotion on ability and so on.

D. *People on the Present Job*

Co-workers of an employee influence his total job satisfaction. The Hawthorne studies highlighted the importance of interpersonal relationship on a job. If a worker associates with people who are committed and are motivated, he could get motivated and increase his productivity. Interest and enthusiasm are infectious. The JDI attempts to find out

from the worker if co-workers are stimulating, boring, slow, ambitious, stupid, fast, responsible, loyal, talk too much, etc.

E. *Supervision on the Job*

The supervisor can make or break an employee. He is nearest to the operative employee and performs the lynchpin function. The way he relates to his subordinate and the way the employees perceive him influence their satisfaction. The supervisor to a large extent determines how organizational favours are distributed. Characteristics such as ask my advice, hard to pause, knows the job well, lazy, influential, impolite etc are included in the JDI scale. The JDI according to Nwachukwu is very useful instrument for measuring job satisfaction. It is not only measures what is available in a job situation but also what an employee perceives he should get from alternatives open to him.

This research work on Job satisfaction and work performance in Kebbi state will therefore bring to lime light the numerous challenges confronting Librarians at work place in Kebbi state in order to know the causes and to proffer solutions for enhancing the problem on ground.

F. *Statement of the Problem*

Academic librarians have the responsibilities of ensuring that the day to day activities of the libraries are carried out efficiently. It is therefore disheartening to know that the librarians sometimes exhibits some indifferent attitudes ranging from lateness to work, abandonment of duties, and unfriendliness among their co-workers, the library users and even the community or the institutions in which they are serving. This gave rise to the reason why the researchers began to investigate why the librarians sometimes act the way they do. Does it mean that they are not satisfied with their jobs, or are their needs not been met in the libraries? Despite the importance of job satisfaction and the challenges posed by lack of it, no study has been carried out on it which justifies the need for this study, Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Librarians in Academic Libraries in Kebbi State.

And to the best of our knowledge, no research has been conducted on Assessment of Job Satisfaction and work Performance among Librarians in Academic Libraries particularly in Kebbi State. Research findings from various studies have shown that there are some relationships between job satisfaction and the various job dimensions such as pay, promotion, supervision, contingent rewards, benefits, communication, the work itself, the operational procedure in the work place and interpersonal relationship among the others [8]. Job satisfaction creates positive attitude, boosts workers moral, which results in improved performance, harmonious relationships with colleagues add a lots. Employee satisfaction at the work place propels productivity. If the academic librarians like every other worker are not satisfied in their job, there will be less or no productivity.

G. *Objectives of the Study*

The objective of this study is to determine the job satisfaction among librarians in academic libraries Tertiary Institution in Kebbi State. The specific objectives are as follows:

- To ascertain the level of satisfaction found among the librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi State.
- To find out the effects of job satisfaction and work performance as perceived by the librarians in Kebbi State.
- To identify the factors responsible for job satisfaction and work performance among the academic librarians in Kebbi State.
- To ascertain the problems associated with job satisfaction and work performance among the librarians in Kebbi State.
- To determine the strategies for enhancing job satisfaction among the librarians academic in Kebbi State.

H. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- What is the satisfaction level of librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi State?
- What are the effects of job satisfaction as perceived by the librarians in Kebbi State?
- What are the factors responsible for job satisfaction or desertification among academic librarians in Kebbi State?
- What are the problems associated with librarian's job satisfaction and work performance among librarians in Kebbi State?
- What are the strategies for motivation and for achieving job satisfaction and work performance among academic librarians in Kebbi State?

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The survey research design was used to conduct the study. Survey is a descriptive study which seeks to describe what exists or the present status of existence or absence of what is being investigated, [9]. The survey research method was adopted for this study because, it involves studying a group of people in a profession by collecting and analyzing data from a few they considered to be representative of the entire group. Furthermore, the survey research design was considered more appropriate for this study due to the fact that it provides the needed logical model of proof that allows the researcher to draw inferences concerning relationships among the variables under investigation.

B. Area of Study

The study was conducted in Kebbi State which is in the North West Geo political zone of Nigeria. Kebbi is a state in north-western Nigeria with its capital at Birnin Kebbi. The state was created out from part of Sokoto State in 1991. Kebbi State is bordered by Sokoto State, Niger State, Zamfara State, Dosso Region in the Republic of Niger and the nation of Benin. It has a total area of 36,800 km² (14,200 sq mi). Kebbi State consists of 21 Local Government Areas (LGAs), four emirate councils (Gwandu, Argungu, Yauri and Zuru), and 35 districts. And it has a total population of 4,440,050 as at 2016 population census. The choice of Kebbi State for this study is because it houses a quite number of functional academic libraries.

C. Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all academic librarians and Senior Library Officers in seven (7) tertiary institutions in Kebbi State including Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State Polytechnic, Dakingari, Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu, School of Nursing and Midwifery, Birnin Kebbi and School of Health Technology, Jega respectively. The distribution is shown in Table 1 below:

Population Distribution of Respondents		
S/N	Name of Institution	Population of Respondents
1	Federal University Birnin Kebbi (FUBK)	12
2	Kebbi State University of Science and Technology (KUSUSTA)	10
3	Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi (WUFEDPOLY)	10
4	Kebbi State Polytechnic, Dakingari (KESPODAK)	6
5	Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu.	6
6	School of Nursing and Midwifery, Birnin Kebbi	1
7	School of Health Technology, Jega	1
Total		46

Table 1

Source: Offices of: The librarians, nominal role (2021)

D. Sample and Sampling Technique

The number of librarians and Senior Library Officers involved will be 46, and so the whole librarians were will be used for the study because of the small size.

E. Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection for this study was questionnaire. The questionnaire was titled Job Satisfaction and Work Performance of Librarians Questionnaire (JSWPLQ) for the purpose of this study. The questionnaire was designed by the researchers, strictly in line with five research questions of the study. The questionnaire was divided in to two parts viz: A and B. Part A asked questions about the background information of the respondents while part B treated levels of job satisfaction and work performance among librarians. The respondents were required to tick (✓) from the appropriate options as provided in the questionnaire.

F. Validation of Instrument

The instrument was validated by the following people using face validation; two lecturers in the department of Library and information Science and One from the Department of Social Science who are experts in research works. They were requested to take critical examination of the questions with the view of determining the appropriateness to the variables being investigated. Their

comments and suggestions were taken into consideration in the final modification of the instrument.

G. Method of Data Collection

The co-researcher and trained research assistants visited the institutions under study for the purpose of administering the questionnaires. They administered copies of the questionnaires to the respondents personally, and with the help of research assistants, collected them back. This method helped in ensuring high return rate of the questionnaires. Out of the total of 46 questionnaires administered 43 questionnaires representing 93.48% response rate were correctly filled and returned. The data analysis was based on the correctly filled and returned questionnaires.

H. Method of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 2.1. Responses to the items in the questionnaire were analyzed using frequency counts and mean. The mean score of 2.50 was used as the benchmark. Any mean score from 2.50 and above indicates that the respondents agreed on that item and any mean score below 2.50 indicates disagreement. The mean values of responses were analyzed using the four-point Likert Scale: 4-Very high satisfaction level, 3-High satisfaction level, 2-Low satisfaction level and 1-No satisfaction level. Similarly, 4-Strongly agree, 3 –Agree, 2-Disagree and 1-Strongly Disagree respectively.

III. RESULTS

A. Research Question One:

What is the satisfaction level of librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi State?

The information used to answer this research question is obtained using items i-viii of the questionnaire. The results of the analysis are presented in table 2 below.

N = 43

Mean Responses of Librarians on level of Satisfaction			
S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
i	I am satisfied with the salary I receive.	2.67	Agree
ii	The communication level with my co-workers is good.	3.42	Agree
iii	The communication link with my supervisor is good.	3.23	Agree
iv	The authority concerned attends to the needs of my library.	3.00	Agree
v	My salary is good and regular.	2.60	Agree
vi	I have good rapport with my Superior officers.	3.21	Agree
vii	There are promotion opportunities for me	3.05	Agree
viii	I am sponsored for workshops and conferences.	2.32	Disagree

Table 2

Table 2 revealed that items i to vii have mean of 2.67, 3.42, 3.23, 3.00, 2.60, 3.21 and 3.05 respectively. These mean scores are greater than the 2.50 benchmark. This

implies that the Librarians in the academic libraries agreed that they are satisfied with the salary they receive, communication level with co – workers and supervisors, authority concerned providing the needs of the workers, regular salary, and commendable rapport with the superior officers as well as promotion opportunities. This finding is consistent with the findings of [10]; [11]; [12]; [13]; [14];[15]; and [16] which revealed that the Librarians in the academic libraries agreed that they are satisfied with the salary they receive, communication level with co – workers and supervisors, authority concerned providing the needs of the workers, regular salary, and commendable rapport with the superior officers as well as promotion opportunities.

However, item viii with mean score of 2.32 indicates that the librarians disagreed that they are sponsored for workshops and conferences. This lends credence to the finding of [17] which casts doubt on the librarians sponsored for workshops and conferences.

B. Research Question Two

What are the effects of job satisfaction and work performance as perceived by the Librarians in Kebbi State?

The information used to answer this research questions are obtained from items i- vi of the questionnaire. The results of the analysis are summarized in table 3.

N = 43

Mean Responses of Librarians on Behavior when Not Satisfied			
S/N	Item	Mean	Decision
I	Lateness to work	2.35	Disagree
Ii	Abandonment of duty	2.40	Disagree
iii	Low productivity	2.44	Disagree
iv	Antagonism with colleagues	2.40	Disagree
V	Loss of morale	2.70	Agree
vi	Poor quality of output	2.65	Agree

Table 3

The results presented in table 3 shows that items i to iv have mean scores 2.35, 2.40, 2.44, 2.40 and 2.70 respectively. Apparently these mean scores are below the 2.50 benchmark. This shows that the respondents disagreed on these items. This in line with the findings of [18] who asserted that the implication is that even when not satisfied with the conditions of work, the librarians do not resort to lateness to work, abandonment of duty, low productivity and antagonism with colleagues. However the result in items v-vi with means scores 2.70 and 2.65 indicated that not been satisfied can lead to loss of morale and poor output as revealed in a study conducted by [19] and Locke [6] which does not revealed divergent opinion.

C. Research Question Three

What are the Factors responsible for job satisfaction or dissatisfaction among academic Librarians in Kebbi State?

The information used to answer this research question are sort using items i - v of the research questions. The results are summarized in table 4.

N = 43

Mean Responses of Librarians on Factors Responsible for Job Satisfaction			
S/N	Item	Mean	Decision
I	Ill health is a factor for retrenchment in my library	2.72	Agree
Ii	I must come to work even when my salary is delayed.	3.07	Agree
Iii	The rules and policies in my library are rigid.	2.72	Agree
Iv	The environment affects my job positively.	2.95	Agree
V	My subordinates are friendly	3.18	Agree

Table 4

From table 4, items i to v have mean scores of 2.72, 3.07, 2.72, 2.95 and 3.18 respectively, which are greater than the 2.50 benchmark. Therefore, the librarians agreed that Ill health is a factor for retrenchment, coming to work even when salary is delayed, rigid library policies, positive effect of the environment on the job and friendly subordinates are the factors responsible for job satisfaction and work performance which does not contradict the finding of [20]; [21] whose research finding is aligned with that of the current study.

D. Research Question Four

What are the problems associated with Librarians job satisfaction and work performance among Librarians in Kebbi State?

The information needed to answer this research question are obtained using items i to ii and analyzed, the results are presented in table 5.

N = 43

Mean Responses of Librarians on Problems Associated with Job Satisfaction			
S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
I	There are opportunities for socialization	3.02	Agree
ii	There are no promotion opportunities for me	2.12	Disagree
iii	My superior officer has no good administrative and managerial skills	2.02	Disagree
iv	There is no room for personal growth on the job.	2.21	Disagree

Table 5

Table 5 revealed that items i with a means scores as 3.02 agreed that there are opportunities for socialization in the Libraries as revealed in the research findings of [19] and [6]. Whereas items ii to iv with means scores 2.12, 2.02 and 2.21 which were below the stipulated benchmark of 2.50 indicated disagreement which means that there is promotion opportunities, superior officer has administration and managerial skills, no room for personal growth on the job exist in the library which goes contrary to the research findings of [9]. Therefore, these are not the problems associated with job satisfaction and work performance in the academic libraries.

E. Research Question Five

What are the strategies for motivation and for achieving job satisfaction and work performance among academic librarians in Kebbi State?

The information used to answer this research question are obtained using item i – viii and analyzed. The results are summarized in table 6 below.

N = 43

Mean Responses of Librarians on Strategies to Enhance Job Satisfaction			
S/N	Item	Mean	Decision
I	Strategies for achieving job satisfaction is clear	3.19	Agree
Ii	I always go on annual leave	2.79	Agree
Iii	I have medical coverage	2.53	Agree
Iv	My supervisor shows appreciation for job well done	2.94	Agree
V	My subordinates are competent	2.98	Agree
Vi	I receive financial rewards as appreciation for job well done	2.13	Disagree
vii	My subordinates are respectful and friendly	3.14	Agree
viii	My subordinates are always ready to co operate with me	3.07	Agree

Table 6

From table 6, items i-v, vii and viii have mean scores of 3.19, 2.79, 2.53, 2.94, 2.98, 3.14 and 3.07 respectively which are above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, the librarians agreed that strategies for achieving job satisfaction are clear, going on annual leave, medical coverage, appreciation from supervisor for job well done, competent subordinates, respectful and friendly subordinates who are ready to cooperate are strategies for enhancing job satisfaction. This is consistent with the study conducted by [5]. However, the librarians disagreed that receiving financial reward as appreciation for job well done is not a strategy for enhancing job satisfaction and work performance in academic libraries in Kebbi State as evident in the research output of [14] that sees financial reward not as determining factor for employee’s job satisfaction and work performance.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The following findings can be deduced from this study:

A total number of Fourty three (43) academic librarians and senior library officer (HND Cadre) in academic libraries in Kebbi State were the population for this study. This study was carried out based on five research questions: what is the satisfaction level of librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi state?, what are the effects of job satisfaction and work performance as perceived by the librarians?, what are the factors responsible for job satisfaction and dissatisfaction?, what are the problems associated with librarians job satisfaction and work performance, what are the strategies for encouraging motivation and for achieving job satisfaction and work performance in academic libraries?. After collecting the data and analyzing them, the following findings were derived from the study:

- There is commendable level of job satisfaction and work performance among the librarians, except for workshops and conferences where they disagreed with a mean score of 2.32 which fall below the stipulated benchmark of the study.
- The librarians do not resort to lateness to work, abandoning duty, low productivity, antagonism with colleagues when they are not satisfied with their job. They however opined that dissatisfaction can lead to loss of morale and poor quality of output.
- The results found that ill health is not a factor for retrenchment, they must come to work even when their salary is delayed, the rules and policies in the libraries are rigid, the environment affects their jobs positively, and that their subordinates are friendly.
- The result further revealed that, it is clear that there are opportunities for socialization, however they have no promotion opportunities, the library superior officers have administrative skills and that there is also room for personal growth on the job.
- There are clear strategies for achieving job satisfaction, they go on annual leave, they have medical coverage, their supervisors appreciates them for a job well done, their subordinates are competent, respectful and always ready to co operate. But disagreed that that they receive financial reward as appreciation for job well done.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Librarians should be sponsored to workshops and conferences if not they may not be enlightened about the current trends in librarianship which they might have learnt from their counter parts from other libraries or library schools. This will also enable them to acquire more knowledge and become more competent in executing their duties.
- Annual leave and medical coverage are the factors identified to enhance job satisfaction and work performance. Hence the researchers recommend that these factors should be enshrined as regular benefits of the workers in these academic libraries. These will give the librarians sense of security and care.
- There is need for recruitment of more qualified Librarians to strike a balance of Librarians/User ratio to make the Library services more effective as the study revealed limited number of qualified librarian in the Institutions under study.
- There should always be opportunities for socialization in the libraries to ease their stress and relax their nerves, this might give them the opportunity to crack jokes, play games as the case may be, and hence a happy worker is a productive worker.
- Authority concerned should always attend to the needs of these libraries, supply them with good and current library tools and equipment, this will encourage them to carry out their duties effectively and efficiently.

VI. CONCLUSION

Job satisfaction and work performance among employees in academic libraries is a driving force in obtaining quality library services in Kebbi State. The study accessed the levels of job satisfaction and work performance, factors affecting job satisfaction and work performance and strategies to enhance job satisfaction and work performance. The study was guided by five research questions. The survey research design was used to conduct the study. The population of the study consisted of all librarians and Senior Library Officers in the institutions under study. 46 academic librarians and Senior Library Officer were used as the sample for the study. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The researchers administered copies of the questionnaires and with the help of research assistants collected them back. The research questions were the basis for data analysis. From the results obtained, the researchers discovered that the level of job satisfaction and work performance among workers in academic libraries in Kebbi State is commendable. The salary, interpersonal communication and administration, worker relationships are the qualities that characterize the level of job satisfaction among the workers in the academic libraries. The researchers also observed that for enhancement of job satisfaction and work performance in the academic libraries, the following strategies are very relevant: annual leave, having respectful, friendly and competent subordinates as well as medical coverage. The librarians should be sponsored for workshops and conferences to enable them to acquire more knowledge and competence. It was recommended that the librarians should always be granted annual leave and medical coverage as these would give them a sense of security and care. This study is limited to only academic libraries in Kebbi state, therefore, inferences and conclusions made on the study are only applicable to these academic libraries. Job satisfaction and work performance of academic librarians in other states of the federation should be looked at so that the findings put together will be used for generalization.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Ekere, F.C. Administration of Academic Libraries: A Book of Readings. Praise House Publishers: Enugu, 2016.
- [2.] Ode, E.O. & Omokaro, D.A. Basic Principles and Practice of Librarianship. Nigeria: PSG Publications., 2017.
- [3.] Ifidon, S.E. Essentials of Management for African University Libraries. Lagos: Libri service. 1985.
- [4.] Obodoeze, F.O. A first course in Library Science. Nimo: Rex Charles & Patrick Limited. 2011.
- [5.] Maslow, A.: Motivation and Personality 2nd WEdition, New York: Harper and Row Publishers, 2013.
- [6.] Locke, E.A.: What is job satisfaction? Journal of Organizational Behavior and Human Performance. 4,309 – 336., 2016.
- [7.] Nwachukwu, C.C.: Management, Theory and Practice, Onitsha: Africana, 2011.
- [8.] Thompson G.J.: Job Satisfaction of Vocational Teachers in Puerto Rico, Unpublished Doctorial Dissertation, The Ohio State University , Columbus, 2014.

- [9.] Ali, G. M: Academic library job satisfaction in Nigeria: A case study of Enugu and Ebonyi States. Unpublished B. Ed. Project, University of Nigeria, Ibadan, 2016.
- [10.] Albanese, R. A.:Take this job and loveit. Library Journal, 36-39, 2008.
- [11.] Olorunsola, E. O: Job performance of administrative staff in South West Nigeria Universities, European Journal of Educational Studies, 4(3), 333-337.
- [12.] Babalola, G.A. & Nwalo, K.I.N. Influence of job motivation on the productivity of librarians in colleges of education in Nigeria. Information and Knowledge Management, 3 (5), 70 – 75. 2013.
- [13.] Oluchi, P. & Ozioko, R.E.: Job satisfaction among librarians in academic libraries in Niger State.International Research Journal of Library & Information Science, 4(3), 406 - 416., 2014.
- [14.] Ademodi, D.T. &Akintomide, O.A.: A comparative study of levels of job satisfactionamong librarians in private and public universities in Ondo State.Journal ofInformation and Knowledge Management, 5 (11), 1-9., 2015.
- [15.] Darbar, M.R. (2015).Job satisfaction among librarians of college libraries of Vallabh Vidyangar. The International Journal of Indian Psychology, 2 (3), 26– 29.Paper ID:IJIPS2015020308.
- [16.] Vijayabanu, U. &Swaminathan, V.D.: Relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment on coping with organization change. International Journal of Information Research and Review, 3, (73-81)., 2016.
- [17.] Japheth, A. Y.” Job satisfaction among librarians in Nigerian public universities; Journal of Library Services and Technologies; 1(1), 73-92, 2019.
- [18.] Weiss, H.M: Deconstructing job satisfaction: separating evaluations, beliefs and affective experiences. Human Resource Management Review, 12, 173 – 194., 2016.
- [19.] Invancevich J.M.: A Study of the Impact of Management by Objective on perceived Need Satisfaction Personnel Psychology Vol, 23, 1970 kalm Robert I. “Productivity and Job Satisfaction” Personnel Psychology Vol. 3, No., 13. autumn 2017.
- [20.] Rosnowski, M. &Hulin, C.: The scientific merit of valid measures of general constructs with special reference to job satisfaction and job withdrawal. In C.J. Cranny (Ed.) Job satisfaction: How People Feel About their Jobs and How it Affects their Performance. Lexinton books: New York., 2012.
- [21.] Szymanski, E.M. & Hershenson, D.B. : Career development of people with disabilities: An Ecological model. In R.M. Parker & Szymanski (Eds.). Rehabilitation of counseling: Basic and Beyond (3rd Ed). Austin, TX: pro- Ed. Retrieved from www.umb.edu on march, 2022.